

The Causal Effect of Volume on Health Gains from Hip Replacement Surgery: Evidence from England

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Larger hospitals are assumed to provide better quality of care, due to greater surgical experience and/or more standardised processes of care. This volume-outcome association has been reported in the literature, but the evidence of a causal effect of surgical volume on quality remains scarce. Furthermore, few studies have looked beyond ‘failure measures’ such as mortality or readmission rates. Understanding whether the observed association is causal and how it benefits patient health is highly relevant in the context of policies that aim to concentrate care or to increase hospital competition. The objective of this paper is to investigate the causal effect of hospital and surgeon volume on health improvements for elective (i.e. planned) hip replacement patients in the English NHS.

Data: We link together routine administrative data (Hospital Episodes Statistics) and patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs) at the patient level for all public hospitals in England for the financial year 2015/16. Patients report their pain and functioning shortly before and six months after the surgery as part of the national PROM survey. We use the Oxford Hip Score (OHS), which is a hip-specific patient-reported measure of health status.

Methods: We regress the post-operative OHS on volume, and control for hospital and patient characteristics. We are able to adjust for patient case-mix with a large number of patient medical and socioeconomic variables reported in the administrative hospital data (e.g. age, sex, medical risk factors, comorbidities, socio-economic status). Importantly, our model also includes controls for the pre-operative health status and how long the patient has lived with symptoms prior to surgery. By using hip-specific risk-adjustment variables, we aim to reduce the bias due to unobserved patient severity in the estimation of the volume-outcome effect. Volume-outcome effect may be subject to an endogeneity bias if hospitals with higher quality enjoy a reputation effect and attract more patients. We address the reverse causality issue which arises from hospital demand’s responsiveness to quality, by constructing a measure of hospital volume that is exogenous to quality. Specifically, we estimate a patient-level model of hospital choice (multinomial logit model) as a function of exogenous factors of hospital choice such as, chiefly, patient’s distance from the hospital. We then replace the observed volumes by the predicted (exogenous) volumes in our OLS regression. This allows us to obtain a causal effect of hospital volumes on health outcomes in the context of elective hip replacements in the English NHS.

Findings: Preliminary results suggest that the observed volume-outcome effect at the hospital level is clinically small in the context of elective hip replacement and is no longer statistically significant once we account for the endogeneity of volume. Further analyses will be conducted to analyse the volume effect at the surgeon level.